

IJTIMOYIY-PSIXOLOGIK MOSLASHISH JARAYONIDA NUTQ NUQSONIGA EGA BOLALARNING RIVOJLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada nutq nuqsoniga ega bolalarning ijtimoiy-psixologik moslashish xususiyatlari, o’zgaruvchan ijtimoiy-psixologik sharoitlarga moslashish masalalarini olimlar tomonidan tahlil etilishi va maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni moslashuvi mexanizmi haqida batafsil yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ijtimoiy-moslashish, nutq, bilish jarayonlar, assotsiativ xulq-atvor, nevroitik reaksiya, ikkilamchi affektiv buzilish, sensor, intellektual, affektiv-irodaviy soha.

Keyingi yillarda mamlakatimiz hayotida yuz berayotgan o’zgarishlar jamiyat rivojlanishi, ijtimoiy munosabatlarning o’zgarishi barcha sohalar kabi bolalarni ta’lim va tarbiyasiga ham o’z ta’sirini ko’rsatdi. Ta’lim maqsadlari va vositalarini o’zgarishida ko’pchilik olimlar bolalarni ijtimoiy-psixologik sharoitlarga moslashuvini farqlaydilar, mikro va makroguruhlarda dinamik tizim sifatida o’zaro aloqa o’rnatishi; shaxsni rivojlanishi va bolani ijtimoiy muhitga kirishdagi shaxslararo va tashqi muhitga moslashuvi.

Ijtimoiy-psixologik adaptatsiyaga shaxs imkoniyatlarini to’liq yuzaga chiqaruvchi ijtimoiy aloqa jarayoni sifatida qaraladi.

SHaxs imkoniyatlari o’zida o’z-o’zini boshqarish va o’zgartirilgan sharoitda o’zini tutishni ta’minlovchi o’z-o’zini anglashni rivojlanish darajasi va shaxsiy resurslar yig’indisini aks ettiradi.

O’zgaruvchan ijtimoiy-psixologik sharoitlarga moslashish yetarlicha murakkab kechadi. Jamoaga kirish, shuningdek ijtimoiy-psixologik sharoitlarga moslashish, ko’p hollarda havotirlanish, noqulayliklar, faollikning pasayishi va hatto sog’liqni yomonlashuvi bilan birga kechadi.

Ko’pincha inson assotsiativ xulq-atvorga, nevroitik reaksiyalarga va boshqa moslashishga to’sqinlik qiluvchi hodisalarga olib keluvchi yangi sharoitga moslasha olmaydilar.

Keyingi vaqtlarda maktabgacha ta’lim muassasalariga moslasha olmaydigan bolalar soni ortib borayotgani kuzatilmogda. 3 yoshdagi krizis davri nafaqat bola shaxsini (L.S.Vigotskiy, D.B.Elkonin) (71) va asab tizimini rivojlanishi uchungina emas, balki nutq rivojlanishi uchun ham senzitiv davr hisoblanadi. (E.A.Dyakova, Ye.M.Mastyukova) (39) Bu maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni nutqiy rivojlanishiga ta’sirini aniqlashga, uni yangi ijtimoiy-psixologik sharoitlarga moslashuviga ta’sir ko’rsatadi.

Nutqiy faoliyat kichik maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni moslashuvi mexanizmi komponentlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Nutqiy rivojlanish darajasi moslashuv muvaffaqiyatlari olimlaridan biridir.

Nutqiy faoliyat sensor, intellektual, affektiv-irodaviy sohalarda kechuvchi barcha psixik jarayonlar bilan uzviy bog’liqlikda shakllanadi va amalga oshadi. Kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalardagi nutqiy yetishmovchilik ularning umumiy rivojlanishiga ta’sir ko’rsatadi: psixik funksiyalarni shakllanishini to’xtatadi, bilish imkoniyatlarini chegaralaydi, ijtimoiy moslashuv jarayonini buzadi.

Ko'p hollarda bunday bolalarda moslashish og'ir kechadi, bu nevroitik reaksiyalarni paydo bo'lishida, havotirli-ko'rquvchi buzilishlarda va boshqalarda aks etadi.

Qo'rquv va havotir ikkilamchi affektiv buzilish sifatida duduqlanuvchi, NTR, dizartrik, alalik bolalarda kuzatilishi haqida ayrim, ammo yetarlicha tizimlashtirilmagan ma'lumotlar mavjud. (V.I.Seliverstov) (50) Turli nutq nuqsonliriga ega bolalar havotirli-ko'rquv holatini rivojlanishi bo'yicha xavf-hatar guruhini o'zida aks ettiradi, chunki ularda atrof-olam nafaqat yetilmagan, balki kamyob sensor va xissiy tizimlar orqali tushuniladi.

Har qanday qo'rquv yoki sababsiz havotir bola xulq-atvorini sezilarli darajada o'zgartirib, bu uni psixik rivojlanishiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi, uni xarakter sifatlarini o'zgartiradi ta'lim va tarbiyasiga negativ ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Qo'rquv sababli sodir bo'ladigan psixik o'zgarishlar ontogenetik ijtimoiylashuv jarayonini buzilishiga, shaxsning ijtimoiy-psixologik yakkalanishini rivojlanishiga olib keladi.

Bunday affektiv holatlarni paydo bo'lishi uchun senzetiv davr-“inson-insonga” munosabatlari tizimini murakkablashuvi yoki almashinishi davri hisoblanadi. (V.N.Myasimov, A.M.Prixojan) (26, 27). Maktabgacha yoshda bunday emotsional-stresli omillar bilan paydo bo'ladigan va qo'rquv-xavotirli reaksiyalarni chuqurlashtiradigan omillar bolani ta'lim muassasalariga birlamchi moslashish davri hisoblanadi. (N.D.Vatugina, A.I.Zaharova, A.A.Kolchadjyan, A.A.Solntseva, R.V.Tonkova-Yampalskaya)

Tadqiqotchilar (V.I.Seliverstov) (50) bunday bolalarda o'zining nuqsoniga nisbatan e'tibor qaratishi va unga nisbatan turli munosabatda bo'lishi haqida fikr bildiradilar. (havotir, qo'rquv, ishonchsizlik).

Zamonaviy bolalar psixologiyasi va psixoterapiyasida xavotirli-ko'rquv holatini korrektsiyalashga integrativ yondoshuv ancha keng tarqalgan. Situativ va shaxsiy havotirni korrektsiyalashda kognitiv- xulq-atvor strategiyasidan keng foydalaniladi. Bolalarda fiziologik paydo bo'ladigan havotirni korrektsiyalashda mutaxassislar xulq-atvor yondoshuviga murojaat qilib, relaksatsiya metodini qo'llaydilar. Negativ kechinmalarni korrektsiyalashda kognitiv-xulq-atvor metodlari qo'llaniladi, ular bolalarni havotirli sharoitlarni baholash va tahlil qilishga o'rgatadi, ularni bartaraf etish yo'llarini kengaytiradi, kuchli havotirda o'z-o'ziga yordam berish usullarini qo'lash, o'zining o'tgan va hozirgi sharoit malakalaridan o'z-o'zini himoya qilish strategiyalarini izlashga o'rgatadi.

O'z-o'ziga baho berish va shaxslararo konflikt (nizo)larni korrektsiyalashda, o'z-o'zini anglash orqali reorientatsiyadan, havotir va nevroitik nizolarni anglash, “ideallashtirilgan “Men” ni yolg'onligini anglash bilan birga ichki nizolarni bartaraf etish strategiyalari ishlab chiqiladi, erkin, spontan o'yinlar uchun sharoitlar yaratiladi, nizoli sharoitlardagi hissiy bosimlardan qutilish uchun nizoli sharoitlar yaratiladi, hikoyalar gapirib beriladi, rasmlar ko'rsatiladi. Yosh bolalardagi korrektsion ishlarni samaradorligini oshirish uchun oilaviy muhitlarni o'zgartirishga qaratilgan metodlarni qo'llash kerak, ota-onalardan birortasi bola-ota-ona terapevtik guruhida qatnashishi lozim bu ota-onalarga maslahat berish va o'qitish, tarbiyachilarni muloqot ko'nikmalariga o'rgatishga qaratiladi, shuningdek bolalarda ota-onalarga nisbatan turli shakldagi negativ ta'sirlarga nisbatan havotirni susaytiruvchi maxsus psixologik mashg'ulotlar, shaxsni faol hayotiy o'rnini egallashini shakllantirishga yo'naltirilgan korrektsion metodlar o'tkaziladi.

SHuningdek, nutq nuqsoniga ega bolalarni atrofidagi ijtimoiy muhitga moslashishni nafaqat ob'ektiv sabablar: ehtiyoj, nutqiy muloqot motivatsiyasi va yo'nalganligiga, balki ota-onalarning faol hayotiy pozitsiyalariga ham bog'liqdir. Erta reabilitatsiya ota-onalarni o'z vaqtida mutaxassisga murojat etish zarurligini tushunganida bo'lishi mumkin. Nutq nuqsoniga ega

ko'pchilik bolalar turli toifadagi mutaxassislar, tarbiyachi, bolalar psixiatri, nevrolog, shuningdek surdolog, okulist, endikrinolog, vrach-genetik maslahatlari yordamiga muhtoj bo'ladi.

Havotirli-qo'rquv holatlarini aniqlovchi asosiy metodlar: bolalar va ota-onalardan qo'rquv holatlari haqida anketa olish (A.I.Zaharov so'rovnomasi), moslashuv jarayonini kuzatish metodikasi (L.V.Kuznetsova), havotirlanish testi (V.Amen, M.Doki, R.Temml), “Qo'rqinchli tush” ertagi mavzusidagi rasm (A.Dyuss ertagi).

Maktabgacha yoshdagi nutq kamchiligiga ega bolalarda xususan havotirning o'rtacha darajasi kuzatiladi, ammo tengdoshlari bilan muloqot sharoitida turli xil nutq kamchiliklariga ega barcha bolalarda esa-yuqori daraja kuzatiladi. Moslashuv parametrini sifatli tahlil qilish shuni ko'rsatadiki: kunduzgi tush, emotsional holat, bolalarni kattalar bilan aloqasi, qoidalarga amal qilish, o'yindagi faollik yuqori ko'rsatkichlar hisoblanib, bolalarni bog'langan zonalarini korreksiyalaydi va havotirli-qo'rquv holatlarini chuqurlashuvi yoki paydo bo'lishi manbai bo'lib xizmat qilishi mumkin.

Havotirli-qo'rquv holati bolalarni moslashuv imkoniyatini taxminiy faraz qilish masalasida shaxsni rivojlanishidagi buzilishlarni aniqlash imkonini beradi va ba'zi tendentsiyalarni aynan, depressiv shaxsni shakllanishi xavfini aniqlash imkonini beradi.

SHunday qilib, yaxshi nutqiy muhit, nuqsonni o'z vaqtida aniqlash, korreksion ishni to'g'ri tashkil etilishi, barcha mutaxassislarning o'zaro aloqasi bolada hissiy yondoshish berish va kattalar bilan ham, tengdoshlari bilan ham, nutqiy muloqotda bo'lish o'yin jarayonida ham qatnashish xohishini yaratadi, o'zining nutqiy ko'nikmalarini oson rivojlantiradi va takomillashtiradi, shu tariqa nutq kamchiliklariga ega bolalarni maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalariga moslashuvini kechishini osonlashtiradi.

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